

Impact of Job Stress on Employees Commitment among the Faculty Members of Um Panabo College

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Abstract. *The main objective of this study is to establish the relationship between the impact of job stress and employees commitment among the faculty members of UM Panabo College. The researchers used the descriptive correlation design in complete enumeration. The statistical tools used in the study were the Mean and Pearson-r. The independent variable of the study was a job stress, its indicators were workload stress, job security stress, and shift work stress. On the other hand, the dependent variable of this study was commitment, its indicators were affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. The result of the computation using is 0.026 of P-value which is less than the alpha of 0.05. Thus, it was found out that there was a significant relationship between the impact of job stress and employees commitment among the faculty members. The findings of the study imply that job stress has an impact on employees commitment of UM Panabo College.*

Keywords: Job Stress, Employee commitment

I. Background of the Study

There have been significant changes in the role of human resources today due to changes in an increasingly complex environment. Employees as assets are the determining resource for the success and achievements of an organization. Human resources play an important role in supporting employees that are qualified and competent as well as innovative, professional, open and flexible. Thus, it is important to learn how to build the best workplace involvement style and the level to ensure retention of successful employees. This way committed employees are extremely pleased and fulfilled by their jobs. However, there is a factor why employees practice the habits of lateness, absenteeism, and turnover. Also, employees could be frustrated, react inadequately and withhold his / her effort or even loaf of work. Hence, employees are more inclined to participate in withdrawing actions and often transfer their loyalty to a different organization and disregard room for improvement (Irefin & Mechanic, 2014).

In Pakistan, a study showed that there is no amount of time to support employees and their working day can be extended by 9 a.m. towards 5 p.m. which a source of concern of the employees. Stress has a negative relation on employees. Over stressed due to time pressure in work life can decrease a level of commitment with work and organization (Bashir & Ramay, 2010).

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, research in Vigan revealed that teachers have least degree of attachment despite the fact that all of them find a sense of economic security in the school. In the other way around, (Gempes, 2008) found that Baby Boomers faculty in Davao City have higher level of affective commitment as compared to Generation X faculty. Moreover, both the Baby Boomers and Generation X faculty demonstrated the same level of continuance commitment (Chavez, 2012).

As interviewed by the researchers, some of the faculty members expressed their concerns about feeling stress due to impromptu reports, paperwork, working environment, work overload, student attitudes, and lack of participation. These things affect their working life in relation to commitment towards work (Personal Interview, September 12, 2019).

Thus, the researchers are motivated to conduct the study about the impact of job stress on employee commitment among the faculty members. The researchers aim to address the work stressors met by teachers and give them the needed appropriate actions.

II. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

According to the anchored theory of Butt (2009), job stress is costly and knowledgeable at both the individual and the organizational level. Employees commitment may be adversely affected by stressful circumstances, although it should be noted that some occupations are considered to be inherently more stressful than others. If appropriate action is not taken, it may result in a reduction in productivity and a high turnover, resulting in a loss of profits and a dent in the bottom line of the organization.

As supported by Makanjee (2006), employees' commitment in the workplace can take various forms (affective, normative, continuance) and can impact the productivity of the organizational effectiveness and the health of employees. Based on the convergence of the understanding of employees regarding their work, their organization, and human interactions, which put these individuals together, the work experience evolves. Employee expectations play a key role in choosing to join, remain, or exit the group. Consequently, an improvement in the workload may contribute to an increase in work stress, the diminished dedication of the employees, and inevitably bad service.

III. Conceptual Framework

As shown in the figure below the conceptual paradigm of the study. The independent variable is job stress with indicators of workload stress defined that a person might feel under pressure if the demands of work are greater than they can comfortably manage. Second is job security stress which refers to a stress that can cause physical, emotional and behavioral problems that can affect professional relationship and well-being. Lastly, shift work stress may shortened a lifespan cause by a person who worked rotating night and generally feeling of being unwell (Butt, 2009). Also, the dependent variable is employees commitment with indicators of affective commitment defined as the emotional attachment to the organization. Second, continuance commitment is the degree to which a person believed that leaving the organization would be costly and the last indicator is normative commitment that has been generally defined how much employees feel they should stay at their organization (Makanjee, 2006).

Figure 1. The Conceptual Paradigm showing the variables of the study

IV. Research Objectives

This study was conducted to determine the relationship of the impact of job stress and employee's commitment among the faculty members. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the impact of job stress on employees commitment among the faculty members in terms of:
 - 1.1 workload stress;
 - 1.2 job security stress; and

- 1.3 shift work stress?
2. What is the level of commitment among the faculty members in terms of
 - 2.1. affective commitment;
 - 2.2. normative commitment; and
 - 2.3. continuance commitment?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the impact of job stress on employees commitment among the faculty members.

V. Research Design

The researchers utilized the descriptive-correlation method. According to Sekaran (2003) notes that a descriptive analysis is carried out such that the properties of the interest variables in a scenario can be ascertained and defined. Descriptive studies are now being carried out to get an understanding of the nature of organizations. Throughout this study, the correlation is often used to identify relevant variables related to the problem. This research employs a method of description as the two variables and method of analysis are defined by explaining the relationship between job stress and the employee's commitment among the faculty members.

VI. Research Subject

The respondents of this study were the faculty members of UM Panabo College; from senior high school with 6 members and 40 from college. The researchers utilized the complete enumeration method since the populations of the said respondents are manageable. The total numbers of respondents are 46.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tool utilized in this study.

Mean. This was utilized to determine the level of job stress and employees commitment.

Pearson-r. This was utilized to determine the relationship between the impact of job stress on employees commitment.

Research Instrument

The instrument utilized in deciding the respondents' reaction within the independent variable and dependent variable was the researchers' adopted questionnaire. The research questionnaire was comprised of two parts, namely: part one, which relates to the impact of job stress and part two refers to the employees commitment among the faculty members which validated by.

To determine the level of the impact of job stress, the following 5 Point Likert type scale was be used:

Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	Interpretations
4.21 - 5.00	Very High	This means that job stress is always manifested.
3.41 - 4.20	High	This means that job stress is oftentimes manifested.
2.61 - 3.40	Moderate	This means that job stress is sometimes manifested.
1.81 - 2.60	Low	This means that job stress is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.80	Very Low	This means that job stress is never manifested.

To determine the level of the employee’s commitment, the following 5 Point Likert type scale was be used:

Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	Interpretations
4.21 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the employees commitment is always satisfactory.
3.41 – 4.20	High	This means that the employees commitment is oftentimes satisfactory.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	This means that the employees commitment is sometimes satisfactory.
1.81 – 2.60	Low	This means that the employees commitment is seldom satisfactory.
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	This means that the employees commitment is never satisfactory.

VII. Results

Level of Job Stress among the faculty members

The level of job stress is measured in terms of workload stress, job security and, shift work stress. The assessment was based on twelve items questions relating to the job stress among the faculty members. As shown in Table 1 is the level of job stress among faculty members of with a grand mean of 3.09 described as moderate descriptive. It means that the level of job stress is sometimes manifested. According to Hussung (2015), Job stress could not be misled on hurdles to learning and gaining new skills.

The first indicator is *workload stress* with an overall mean of 2.94 described as moderate. It means that then level of job stress among faculty members of is sometimes manifested. According to Picincu (2011), a heavy workload can affect the employee’s mood and behavior, which causes poor mental focus, reduced productivity, and difficulty in focusing on the tasks at hand.

The highest item is number 4 with a mean 3.39 described as moderate where faculty members are *responsible for too many people/projects*. This means that optimal pressure helps people to concentrate and do their best. The issues arise when the strain becomes too high. High pressure can make people feel restless, uneasy, and stressed. While the lowest is item number 2 with a mean score of 2.41 describe as a low which states that faculty members experience that *co-worker are inefficient*.

The other item revealed is numbers 3 and 1 with a mean of 3.20 and 2.76 described as moderate where respectively stated that the faculty members experienced *high levels of tome pressure* and *shortage of help at work*.

The second indicator is Job security with an overall mean of 3.30 described as moderate. It means job security is sometimes manifested. According to Dayton, (2019) job security is a guarantee that without the possibility of being unemployed, you can retain your employment.

The highest item is number 2 with a mean of 3.54 described as High where the faculty members *concerning low wages*. This means *the employee reward system* is the key motivating factor for employers to continually aspire for higher wages. It provides them a desire to strive hard to reach the next milestone. While the lowest is item number 4 with a mean score of 3.04 described as a moderate which stated that faculty members *needed ‘PULL’ to get ahead*.

The other item revealed is number 3 and 1 with a mean of 3.50 and 3.11 described as high and moderate where respectively stated that the faculty members *worrying about the poor pension and having fear of being laid off*.

The last indicator is shift work stress with an overall mean of 3.02 described as moderate. It implies that job stress sometimes manifested. According to Ferri, Guadi, Marcheselli, Balduzzi, Magnani & Di Lorenzo (2016), Shift work is one of the more important causes for routine disturbance, contributing to major sleep and biofunctional shifts, which, in effect, will adversely influence the physical and mental health band 's output

The highest item is number 2 with a mean of 3.28 described as moderate were faculty members stated that *Shifting work affects the family life*. This means that shift work will adversely affect the relationship between parents, children, and couples who work evenings that are correlated with greater signs of depression among family members.

While the lowest is number 1 with a mean of 2.74 described as moderate which stated that the faculty members were *feeling chronic effects on mental health*. It means that no significant behavioral wellness programs were open to employees.

The other item revealed is number 3 and 4 with a mean of 3.20 and 2.87 described as moderate where respectively stated that the faculty members of *disruptions* and *feeling uncomfortable while comparing another shift worker*. This means avoid comparing yourself negatively with others at work and instead focus entirely on yourself and your strengths, development, and performance to ensure personal success to achieve the goal.

Table 1
Level of Job Stress among the faculty members

Workload Stress	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Shortage of help at work	2.76	Moderate
2. Co-workers are inefficient	2.41	Low
3. High levels of time pressure	3.20	Moderate
4. Responsible for too many people/projects	3.39	Moderate
Over -all Mean	2.94	Moderate
Job Security		
1. Fear of being laid off/ fired	3.11	Moderate
2. Concerned about low wages	3.54	High
3. Worry about poor pension	3.50	High
4. Need 'PULL' to get ahead	3.04	Moderate
Over-all Mean	3.30	Moderate
Shift Work Stress		
1. Feel chronic effects on mental health	2.74	Moderate
2. Shift work affects the family life	3.28	Moderate
3. Shift work leads to social & domestic disruptions	3.20	Moderate
4. Feel uncomfortable while comparing other shift worker	2.87	Moderate
Over-all Mean	3.02	Moderate
Grand mean	3.09	Moderate

Level of Employees Commitment among the faculty members

The level of commitment was measured through the assessment to faculty members based on the item's questions.

Shown in table 2 is the level of commitment among faculty members which had a grand mean of 3.56 described as High. It indicates that the commitment is very satisfactory. As Alagala, Naakuu & Vito, (2018) *Employees* commitment is the result of the organization that offers employees a workplace climate that maximizes their maximum capacity, enabling them to gain benefit for their commitment. Considerable and successful performance acquisition strategies *are* a vital weapon for enhancing employee participation.

The highest item number 4 with a mean of 4.09 described as high where faculty members *feeling like 'part of the family' at the organization*. This ensures the employees to feel happy together as they experience a good relationship. While the lowest is item number 3 with a mean of 3.28 described as moderate were faculty members *thinking that they could easily become as they attached to another organization as to this one*. This implies that the employees of faculty members felt connected and dedicated to their work.

The second indicator is continuance commitment with an overall mean of 3.26 described as moderate. It means that job commitment is sometimes satisfactory. In the words of Van der Werf (2020), continuance commitment is the dedication to consistency in how workers know they need to remain at their organization. The main reason for their dedication is the desire to continue in the organization. Although there are many factors why we will stay with organizations, but the primary ones being the shortage of working options.

The highest item is number 1 with a mean of 3.48 described as high were faculty members *afraid of what might happen if may quit a job without having another one lined up*. This means that quitting your job is disruptive and creates financial pressure where there was none before. Some people thrive on chaos and urgency, but for many, it creates panic and paralysis. While the lowest is item number 4 with a mean of 2.85 described as moderate which stated that faculty members *wouldn't be too costly to leave organization now*. This means that the lack of viable options will be one of the least significant implications of quitting the organization.

The other items revealed is 3, 8, 2, 5, 7 and 6 with a mean of 3.39, 3.37, 3.35, 3.33, 3.17 and 3.15 described as moderate where respectively stated that faculty members *too much in life would be disrupted if decided to leave organization now, one of the major reasons to work for the organization is that leaving would require considerable personal sacrifice--another organization may not match the overall benefits, ease on organization now*.

The last indicator is the normative commitment with an overall mean of 3.67 described as high. It implies that job commitment is oftentimes satisfactory. According to Van der Werf (2018), normative commitment relates to how much employees remain of their organization. Normatively dedicated employees generally believe they will continue with their organizations. Normatively *committed believes* like quitting their employment will be devastating and feel guilty about the probability of quitting.

The highest item is number 2 with a mean of 4.04 described as high were faculty members *believed a person must always be loyal to his or her organization*. That means employees who contribute to the success of the *organization* and find themselves to be an asset of the *organization*. While the lowest item is number 3 with a mean score of 3.35 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate which states that the faculty members are *jumping from organization to organization does not seem at all unethical*. It implies that loyalty is important and should remain.

The other item revealed the number 4, 1, 7, 6, 8 and 5 with a mean of 3.80, 3.78, 3.74, 3.59, 3.54 and described as high respectively stated that the faculty members were *One of the major reasons to continue to work for the organization believe that the loyalty is important and therefore feel a sense of moral obligation to remain, thinking that people these days move from company to company too often, Things were better in the days when people stayed with one organization for most of their careers, was taught to believe in the value of remaining loyal to one organization, thinking that wanting to be a "company man" or "company woman" is sensible anymore and if got another offer for a better job elsewhere would not feel it right to leave the organization*.

Table 2
Level of Job Commitment among the faculty members

Affective Commitment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	3.80	High
2. I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	3.33	Moderate
3. I think that I could easily become as attached to another organization as I am to this one.	3.28	Moderate
4. I feel like 'part of the family' at my organization.	4.09	High
5. I feel 'emotionally attached' to this organization.	3.87	High
6. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	3.98	High
7. I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization.	4.07	High
Over-all Mean	3.77	High
Continuance Commitment		
1. I am afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another one lined up.	3.48	High
2. It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.	3.35	Moderate
3. Too much in my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.	3.39	Moderate
4. It wouldn't be too costly for me to leave my organization now.	2.85	Moderate

5. Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire.	3.33	Moderate
6. I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.	3.15	Moderate
7. One of the few serious consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.	3.17	Moderate
8. One of the major reasons I continue to work for this organization is that leaving would require considerable personal sacrifice – another organization may not match the overall benefits I have.	3.37	Moderate
Over-all Mean	3.26	Moderate
Normative Commitment		
1. I think that people these days move from company to company too often.	3.78	High
2. I believe that a person must always be loyal to his or her organization	4.04	High
3. Jumping from organization to organization does not seem at all unethical to me.	3.35	Moderate
4. One of the major reasons I continue to work for this organization is that I believe that loyalty is important and therefore feel a sense of moral obligation to remain.	3.80	High
5. If I got another offer for a better job elsewhere I would not feel it was right to leave my organization	3.50	High
6. I was taught to believe in the value of remaining loyal to one organization.	3.59	High
7. Things were better in the days when people stayed with one organization for most of their careers.	3.74	High
8. I think that wanting to be a “company man” or “company woman” is sensible anymore.	3.54	High
Over-all Mean	3.67	High
Grand Mean	3.56	High

Significant Relationship between Job Stress and Employees

Commitment among the faculty members

Table 3 shows the result of the significance of the relationship between job stress and commitment among faculty members. As presented, the overall r-value is 0.328 with a p-value of 0.026 which greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, a significant null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected.

It means, therefore, that there is a significant relationship between job stress and commitment among faculty members. The study supports the proposition of Shirian & Asgarikia (2013) stated that employees' proposals are fulfilled and work; they are highly inspired to obtain the highest standard to accomplish organizational objectives. The organization will do something with the employees and the training done to enhance the efficiency of the organization. This study is further supported by Kappagoda, Sothman & Alwis (2014) has also reiterated that employee engagement is the cornerstone to increasing success in each field. This research leads to *enhance* the organization's overall efficiency.

Table 3

Significant Relationship between Impact of Job Stress and Employees Commitment among faculty members

Correlation Coefficient

	EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT
JOB STRESS	0.328
P-value (0.026) < 0.05	SIGNIFICANT

VIII. Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, the following conclusion is drawn:

1. The level of job stress is moderate.
2. The level of commitment is high.
3. There is a significant relationship between job stress and employees commitment among the faculty members.

IX. Recommendation

Based on the finding and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. The researchers recommend that since the level of job stress is moderate, The Researchers recommend that if the degree of job stress is low, the organization will minimize much further if the four-dimensional model of co-worker relationship aims to create better relationships in operations and to improve operational inefficiency can be proposed and confirmed. Besides, employees may be given training, team buildings, seminars, activities and appreciation system to increase workers' trust in their jobs, employees are motivated and believe that they are part of the organization and are not "pushed aside". Finally, a behavioral well-being evaluation, free health screening and wellness counseling, advice, and self-management services should be given to the employees to resolve their adverse mental health effects, through no-to-low-out-of-pocket health premiums, seminar to health care.

2. The researchers recommend that since the level of employees commitment is high, it can be maintained in that level by bringing transferability attachments to natural places to more general nature attachment, focusing on physiological and restorative effects employees from nature-integrating work environments, factors contributing employee tenure/satisfaction and behaviors occur in the workplace when employees feel a greater connectedness. Second, employers may promote retention strategies to its employees like offering more opportunities to use their skills/abilities at work, job security, compensation, and respectful treatment of all employees at all levels to keep outstanding employees. Lastly, the organization may set realistic expectations from the start, show employees that there is room for them to grow, demonstrate the advantages of where they work and trust them to make them feel they're being treasured by the organization and avoid them from jumping to other organization.

3. The researchers proposed that future research may be conducted to the University of Mindanao Branches to further determine the impact of job stress on employees commitment among the faculty members.

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